

What Makes a Design Study Sustainable in Complex Domains? A Characterisation Framework for Regulated, Stakeholder-Rich Contexts

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Abstract

Design studies are a core methodology in visualisation for solving real-world problems, but applying them in complex domains, such as clinical visual analytics, encounters well-recognised challenges. Existing frameworks provide rigour but often fall short in guiding systematic long-term, cross-disciplinary collaborations and sustainable tool adoption in high-stakes settings. This paper introduces a two-phase framework combining extended domain-characterisation methods and grounded in the established design study methodologies to frame the industry-level precondition analysis from project-specific design. Validated through AI-Enabled Clinical Decision Support Systems (AI-CDSS) case studies, our approach standardises domain constraints upfront, accelerates project onboarding, and lays the groundwork for cross-project comparison for sustainable, scalable visualisation research.

CCS Concepts

• **Human-centered computing** → Visualization design and evaluation methods; • **Software creation and management** → Requirements analysis; • **Applied computing** → Decision analysis; Health care information systems;

1. Introduction

Design studies have become a central methodology in the visualisation field, enabling researchers to advance knowledge through problem-driven, domain-specific inquiry. These studies are not only tools for theory building but are also critical vehicles for translating visualisation theory into practice. Rooted in academia, design studies have increasingly been employed in collaborative projects involving industrial and public-sector partners, where the goal (at least from the non-academic collaborators' perspective) is often to create robust, commercially and operationally practical solutions that must satisfy a diversity of real-world user requirements, institutional priorities, and regulatory frameworks. Over the past two decades, a significant body of research has refined the design study process as the visualisation community has developed strong methodological foundations. The established frameworks offer rigour in describing workflows, evaluating systems, and grounding design decisions. However, as the field matures and more visualisation work is integrated into cross-sector contexts, new challenges have emerged.

These challenges are conspicuously apparent in the health domain, where the stakes of failure are high and the environment is complex. Design studies in healthcare typically involve multidisciplinary teams, sensitive data, ethical oversight, and the need for interoperability with legacy systems. For example, a project to create migraine attack prediction dashboards must account for clinical

trial protocols, patient consent and trust, clinical workflow integration, to name a few. In such contexts, short-term engagements and single-project pipelines are insufficient. There is a growing need for frameworks that anticipate and support long-term, trust-based collaboration.

Increasingly, design is recognised as not simply the creation of artefacts, but the facilitation of participatory, accountable, and infrastructurally entangled change processes. In visualisation research, and more specifically visual analytics, however, the focus is often on more novel techniques and tools, not long-term impact; this is aggravated by the publication bias, as highlighted by Sedlmair et al. [SMM12]. Yet in practice, visual analytics solutions can fail if not conscious of this wider context, thus diminishing their significance. Furthermore, policymakers and research funders are increasingly requiring evidence of impact, ethical foresight, and sustainability in research outputs [Cor19,NTA22]. Visualisation research is no longer viewed as a standalone theoretical pursuit but as a socio-technical intervention with long-term implications for equity, governance, and public accountability (as in visualisation for XAI [KZW25]). This shift has led to corresponding expectations from design study methodologies.

Our work aims to systematically analyse and structure emerging requirements, drawing on established methodologies such as the Nine-Stage Framework [SMM12] and domain characterisation approaches [Mar18,CDHK22]. The Nine-Stage Framework outlines

a linear yet iterative process for visualisation design studies, while domain characterisation focuses on identifying context-specific parameters like tasks, users, and data constraints. While foundational, these methods are not fully geared towards ensuring broad contextual awareness.

This research intersects with longstanding concerns in the area of human-computer interaction (HCI), particularly the chasm between technical prototypes and their sustained, real-world adoption. In the HCI literature, models such as Technology Acceptance Model, Unified Theory of Acceptance and Use of Technology [DRJ*19], socio-technical frameworks like Activity Theory and in a domain-specific context the exemplary NASSS framework [APP*19] have long been used to explain why systems fail to be embedded in practice. With the appreciation of similarity of challenges around user perceptions, institutional alignment, and utility over time, we explore these dynamics as specifically apposite to visualisation design studies. This approach allows us to go beyond descriptive characterisation towards practical operationalisation of these elements for more successful and impactful design studies.

Our research produces a novel framework for design studies that explicitly supports sustainable collaboration between researchers and external partners. By building upon existing methodologies and integrating underexplored dimensions such as organisational dynamics and ethical governance, and embedding these concerns into the early stages of domain characterisation and iterative design stages, our framework brings visualisation research into deeper alignment with domains with the aim to support the design of visual analytics tools that are not only effective but also robust across time, teams, and institutional transitions.

Sociotechnical decisions are particularly pronounced in clinical AI-enabled Decision Support Systems (AI-CDSS), where implementation constraints span compliance mandates, infrastructure limitations, data governance, and human oversight of automated systems. Ethical AI requirements, such as transparency, privacy, and autonomy, are often poorly specified and embedded in shifting legal and cultural contexts. For example, the use of Federated Learning for AI model training raises questions about cross-border data access and auditability. Consequently, design studies often need to start with choices about legal governance, institutional buy-in, and co-development strategies. Yet there is no consistent way to elicit, structure, and visualise such upstream decisions. Our framework development process uses AI-CDSS as a guiding case.

The contributions of this work therefore are:

- A gap analysis of current design study methodologies with respect to long-term industry collaboration.
- An extended model of domain characterisation, incorporating organisational, ethical, and other pertinent dimensions.
- A two-phase iterative framework grounded in the theoretical model of Nine-Stage Framework and real-world stakeholder practices.
- A procedural guidance to support researchers and practitioners in operationalising sustainable collaboration.

The methodology presented here meets the following objectives: consistent with and is put in context of the visualisation research agenda, it provides a nominal process model for design studies led

by industry requirements, and it provides a mental model for reflecting and evaluating design study implementations.

2. Related Work

Research in visualisation design studies spans a range of methodological traditions, from structured workflows and abstraction models to participatory and reflective practices. The design studies have matured substantially, guided by foundational methodologies and analytical frameworks. In this section, we situate our work in relation to established literature, emphasising frameworks, terminology, and domain characterisation techniques that ground our approach. We highlight the methodological evolution through frequently cited frameworks and their implications for long-term, interdisciplinary collaboration, using AI-CDSS as a guiding domain context to shape and reflect on broader principled approach.

2.1. Frameworks and Methodologies in Visualisation Design Studies

Seminal works by Sedlmair et al. [SMM12] and [Mun14] have significantly influenced visualisation research methodologies. Sedlmair et al.'s Nine-Stage Framework provides a structured, iterative process consisting of domain problem identification, data and task abstraction, visualisation and interaction design, evaluation, deployment, and reflective analysis. Each stage explicitly outlines activities to systematically address domain challenges and design constraints, making it one of the most extensively referenced process models in the field.

A foundational approach to designing usable and context-aware tools is offered by Hackos and Redish [HR98], which outlines structured methods for identifying user goals, decomposing tasks, and aligning interface features with actual work practices. Their emphasis on contextual inquiry, role delineation, and iterative validation provides a robust framework for early-stage interface planning, especially in complex, multi-stakeholder environments such as clinical decision support.

Other approaches have built on or diverged from these foundations. McKenna et al.'s Design Activity Framework [MMAM14] introduces flexible overlapping phases (understand, ideate, make, deploy), while [Mar18] stress domain characterisation and context-sensitive expertise extraction. Hall et al. [HBH*20] argue for transdisciplinary immersion as an epistemic and methodological stance. While these models differ in emphasis, they share an acknowledgment that design studies are sociotechnical and iterative. The need to design and evaluate tools in long-term collaborations with practitioners, deep focus on domain needs, and longitudinal assessment in real-world settings have been actively discussed in the visualisation community [PRI18, XCBAR24].

Complementarily, Munzner's Nested Model [Mun09] presents a hierarchical abstraction that structures domain-specific problems into clear layers: domain problem characterisation, data/task abstraction, visual encoding, and algorithm design. The Nested Model is discussed in more detail in the next subsection. In this paper, we primarily use the Nine-Stage and Nested frameworks to structure our framework and terminology.

A different strand of literature focuses on participatory and collaborative practices ([JKKS20, IES*11, KGD*19, ALC*23, HBH*20]. Kerzner and colleagues [KGD*19] synthesised lessons from collaborative visualisation projects and proposed principles such as empathy, shared vocabulary, and iterative alignment. While their contribution addresses interpersonal dynamics, it lacks a procedural structure that can be integrated into a full design study methodology. Similarly, Meyer et al. [MD20] developed criteria for evaluating the rigour of design studies but tackled insufficiently sustainability or cross-sector collaboration.

Many sophisticated visualisation projects suffer from failing acceptance by the targeted audience. Isenberg et al. [IZCC08] proposed a detailed evaluation stage at the beginning of the design process to assess the requirements of the visualisation system to be designed. Early and close collaboration with all stakeholders in the design process leads to more successful visualisation applications being developed [JKKS20].

A group of studies offer a longitudinal perspective, such as Ye et al. [YSM*20] documenting a two-year user-centred design study in scientific visualisation. They highlight challenges such as evolving expectations, role turnover, and the fragility of trust, which are common in long-term projects but rarely addressed in methodological literature. Such work, while highlighting the challenges and provide rich empirical foundations for meta-analysis and methodological refinement, remain limited in prescriptive insights and generalisability and into a broader framework.

Other studies have pointed to structural gaps in existing models. Bach et al. [BKR*23] and Cibulski et al. [CDHK22] argue that existing models underrepresent the complexity of stakeholder roles, the impact of institutional policies, and the presence of conflicting values in collaborative settings. They advocate for extending domain characterisation to include non-user stakeholders such as data owners, regulators, and organisational gatekeepers.

Moreover, literature from fields such as explainable AI [KZW25] and participatory public health modelling [SMS14] reinforce the importance of regulatory foresight, ethical co-design, and ongoing stakeholder negotiation. Yet these lessons are seldom translated into design study practice.

Taken together, these works illustrate the fragmentation in current approaches: robust procedural models exist, but they are rarely integrated with relational, institutional, or ethical considerations. Our work addresses this by embedding these neglected dimensions directly into the design study lifecycle, offering researchers and practitioners a more holistic, actionable methodology for sustainable visualisation design.

2.2. Domain characterisation in Visualisation Research

Domain characterisation is central to visualisation design studies, establishing a clear mapping between real-world domain specifics and abstract visualisation requirements. The Nested Model [Mun09] explicitly prioritises domain characterisation as foundational for subsequent abstraction decisions. Literature advocates deeper engagement with domain experts and critical interrogation of domain specifics to adequately capture user needs, task complexity, and data heterogeneity [Mar18, KGD*19].

Emerging research emphasises additional dimensions beyond conventional user-task-data characterisations, such as regulatory compliance, organisational context, temporal evolution, and knowledge dynamics [PRI18, YSM*20, BKR*23]. Such parameters profoundly influence long-term visualisation deployment and impact yet remain insufficiently integrated into standard frameworks.

2.3. Design Studies in AI-enabled Clinical Decision Support Systems

AI-enabled Clinical Decision Support Systems (AI-CDSS) represent a uniquely challenging visualisation context due to inherent sociotechnical complexity, stringent ethical considerations, and rapidly evolving regulatory frameworks [MAM*19]. This complexity is amplified by ethical AI considerations - encompassing data privacy, interpretability, fairness, and accountability - and emerging technological paradigms such as Federated Learning, designed to navigate cross-border data sharing constraints [BEG*19].

Recent visualisation research specifically addresses these AI-CDSS challenges through targeted frameworks and evaluation approaches. Müller et al. [MRP*16] highlight visual analytics techniques tailored for clinical settings, emphasising iterative co-design processes essential for successful stakeholder alignment. Similarly, recent meta-analyses emphasise tailored evaluation strategies to address the unique ethical and regulatory contexts of clinical AI applications [XCBAR24, PRI18, PL20].

This subfield underscores the critical need for frameworks capable of systematically integrating institutional, regulatory, and ethical parameters throughout the visualisation design lifecycle, positioning visualisation researchers to navigate the complex landscape of AI-CDSS effectively.

Existing methodological frameworks, while robust, predate generative-AI workflows, accelerated technological turnover, and heightened sociotechnical complexity in regulated settings. A timely recalibration is therefore imperative; our research advances precisely this updated paradigm.

2.4. Systematic Synthesis of Design-Study Literature

We executed a rapid, structured thematic synthesis of the visualisation-design-study corpus published 2010-2024. After reviewing records, $n = 36$ full papers met inclusion criteria (explicit reflection, high impact). Reviewers open-coded methods sections using a seed codebook derived from the Nine-Stage Framework, the Nested Model, and domain-characterisation literature. Codes were then axially clustered into 14 “challenge” themes (e.g., temporal commitment, trust, regulatory barriers). Each theme was mapped to the Nine-Stage activities to yield Table 1, while parameters repeatedly cited as influencing tool success (stakeholder flux, ethics, data governance, etc.) were abstracted to a reusable domain-characterisation schema, producing Table 2. It details how these parameters vary dynamically across project stages, underscoring the need for iterative reassessment and alignment.

Table 1: Summary of themes relevant to long-term collaboration in visualisation design studies, including stage-specific strategies and key references.

Theme	Summary	References
Temporal commitment	Short timelines hinder continuity and shared ownership	[SMM12], [YSM*20]
Trust	Emerges slowly, collapses quickly	[YSM*20], [HBH*20]
Stakeholders	Shifting roles; inclusion of non-user stakeholders crucial	[BKR*23], [CDHK22]
Knowledge Asymmetry	Difficulty translating tacit knowledge	[CDHK22], [Mar18]
Goal volatility	Industry goals frequently shift; adaptation required	[HBH*20]
Method opacity	Undocumented process decisions	[MMAM14]
Evaluation misfit	Academic metrics misalign with practice	[XCBAR24], [PRI18]
Power dynamics	Variable stakeholder influence	[BKR*23]
Regulatory barriers	Legal barriers impede progress	[SMS14], [PRI18]
Sustainability planning	Lack of continuity post-deployment	[YSM*20], [OCW*23]
Representation bias	Bias towards user stakeholders	[Mar18], [CDHK22]
Immersion degree	Limited researcher domain understanding	[HBH*20]
Feedback fragility	Iterative loops often incomplete	[KGD*19]
Ownership	Unclear post-deployment control	[YSM*20], [OCW*23]
Ethical oversight	Ethics reviews lack iterative process	[SMS14], [PRI18]

Table 2: Domain characterisation model with parameters mapped to project stages, highlighting evolving focuses.

Parameter	Pre-Project Focus	Evolution During Project	Stage Variability
Task	Broad goal elicitation	Goal refinement, objective updates	'Discover', 'reflect'
Data	Availability, governance assessment	Data structuring, gap management	'Discover', 'implement'
Users	Identify initial roles	Track stakeholder changes	'Cast', 'reflect'
Organisation	Workflow, policy identification	Project fit negotiation	'Cast', 'deploy'
Regulation	Map legal constraints	Policy updates management	'Design', 'deploy'
Knowledge	Domain fluency evaluation	Capture tacit insights	'Learn', 'discover'
Tool Ownership	Define rights, update strategies	Adjustments with stakeholder shifts	'Deploy', 'reflect'
Context	Define relevant success metrics	Adapt metrics to changing contexts	'Winnow', 'deploy', 'reflect'
Time	Assess temporal constraints	Manage timeline adjustments	'Discover', 'deploy', 'reflect'
Ethics	Initial ethical guidelines	Iterative ethical evaluations	'Learn', 'reflect'

3. A Methodology for Two-Phase Design Study

The analysis of related work highlights several persistent challenges and knowledge gaps. Methodological frameworks often assume a static context, overlooking evolving domain-specific parameters. Our thematic synthesis (Tables 1, 2) demonstrates the complexity and variability of such parameters, underscoring the need for systematic and ideally reusable organisational and domain knowledge that transcends individual projects. Based on these findings we design a two-phase approach.

3.1. Why two-phase?

Nine-Stage Framework for design studies (e.g. learn, winnow, cast, etc.) treats domain analysis as an early project-specific step. However, we propose restructuring this framework into two phases - an industry-level precondition analysis followed by a project-specific adaptation - to better capture reusable domain parameters before diving into a particular design problem. This separation is motivated by several factors outlined below:

1. *Reusability of domain knowledge.* Many domain constraints

are stable across projects. By conducting an upfront industry-level analysis, designers create a knowledge base (the characterisation layer) that subsequent projects can leverage. A well-documented characterisation of the AI-CDSS domain can be reused by future researchers as a starting point, improving efficiency and consistency across projects.

2. *Systems context and completeness.* A broader system thinking perspective is needed: traditional one-project-at-a-time studies may overlook these wider system interactions. By dedicating an industry-level phase to these preconditions, we ensure that the "big picture" is understood before tailoring to a specific use-case. This addresses calls in the literature for a broader system approach when evaluating interventions, in particular in our focus domain of healthcare.
3. *Addressing tacit domain knowledge.* Domain experts often hold deeply embedded insights that can be hard to articulate or formalise. An industry-level analysis gives more room to apply knowledge elicitation techniques (e.g. focus groups, cross-domain expert panels) to draw out deep expertise. This structured upfront effort answers the noted lack of explicit guidance on how to conduct domain characterisation.

Figure 1: Two-phase framework for sustainable research–industry collaboration in visualisation design studies. The phases terminology is builds on the Nine-Stage Framework [SMM12].

4. *Ensuring critical preconditions.* Successful implementation of AI-CDSS depends on fulfilling certain preconditions in the domain environment. For example, literature emphasises that having a comprehensive ethical, legal and regulatory framework, strong organisational support, and adequate AI knowledge are essential for adoption. By analysing these factors at the industry level, design teams can identify any gaps or risks early (e.g. if no clear legal liability policy exists) and address them in their designs or stakeholder negotiations. Separating this analysis clarifies which requirements are industry-wide prerequisites versus those that a specific project can adjust or innovate upon.

Therefore, we propose restructuring the traditional Nine-Stage Framework into a clearly articulated two-phase approach: an initial, industry-level precondition analysis followed by a project-specific refinement phase. This restructuring maintains the spirit of thorough domain understanding from the Nine-Stage process, while introducing a layer of reuse and systems perspective that strengthens each subsequent design study. We summarise the approach in the protocol illustration Figure 1. The diagram contrasts an Industry-Precondition phase with a Project Core phase. **Industry-Precondition:** Reusable domain knowledge is assembled through expert interviews, scholarly literature, sector reports, community fora, and the systematic review of ethical, regulatory, and policy documents. **Design Study Core:** Building on this knowledge, the project advances through and extends the Nine-Stage Framework [SMM12], tailoring problem discovery, abstraction, design, evaluation, and reflection to the specific context. At the final, **Reflection** stage, across both phases the framework supports (i) standardisa-

tion of methods and artefacts across projects, (ii) integration and scaling of solutions, (iii) continual evolution and exchange of domain knowledge, and (iv) sustained stakeholder engagement.

3.2. Methodology for Industry-Level Analysis

Building on these foundations, we conducted a two-phase design study reported in Surodina et al. [SVARB24]. In this work, design study included an industry-level precondition analysis and as an output collected and organised parameters the initial AI-CDSS domain characterisation map, with a specific focus on ethical AI factors (as defined and taxonomised by the EU AI Act [SSB24]). The learnings from the study expanded and improved on the initial domain mapping and lead to a formulation of a procedural guidance for industry-level domain characterisation, main stages of which are outlined below.

Domain Expert sampling strategy: We began by identifying a diverse and extended pool of domain expert roles and stakeholders to interview. In the healthcare and research AI context, this includes technical teams, clinicians, data stewards and IT managers, administrators, legal/regulatory experts, health data users and ethicists. A purposive sampling approach is used to maximise the coverage of such roles. For example, to capture regulation knowledge, one might include a medical device regulatory advisor; for workflow and organisation, hospital management and frontline clinicians. We aimed for 10–15 experts. Snowball sampling complemented this (asking interviewees to recommend others) to expand understanding of roles and identify niche experts. This broad expert inclusion reflects the “relevant stakeholders and organisations” that systems research shows are key contextual factors for implementing interventions. Defined in a different way, they are health data generators and consumers.

Interview data collection. We developed a semi-structured interview guide aligned to the domain parameters and a design for a focus-group. Interviews are conducted to elicit information for each parameter – for instance, discussing typical tasks and decision-making needs, or probing regulatory constraints that govern AI tools. In focus group to surface unspoken heuristics and practical reasoning domain experts rely on, we incorporated case-study-based questions and cognitive probes: e.g. asking participants to recount a recent complex case of AI-CDSS implementation, which can reveal implicit workflows and decision cues. Interviewers use prompts to ensure experts articulate not just “what” they do but also why, capturing reasoning, context, and exceptions. The sessions are recorded (with consent) and transcribed for analysis with AI tools (otter.ai in this case).

Supplement interviews with document analysis: reviewing policy documents, clinical guidelines, or standards (for data governance and regulations) to fill any gaps or validate statements. In addition, we conducted a review of institutional policies, national healthcare IT strategies, clinical data governance frameworks, and regulatory guidelines (e.g., GDPR, HIPAA, FDA, and MHRA documentation). This included published compliance manuals, ethical codes of practice, and hospital-specific implementation standards for digital health tools. These sources provided formal constraints and best practices that might not emerge from individual interviews, helping to validate anecdotal insights and enrich the domain

Figure 2: Diversity of expert feedback methods allow for comprehensive capture of industry knowledge, as demonstrated via the case-studies: a) structured workshops with stakeholders; b) focus groups; c) industry ethnography.

parameter definitions with authoritative requirements. This triangulation ensures the domain characterisation is not only grounded in practice but also aligned with legal and institutional expectations.

After data collection, we performed a **thematic analysis**, coding the transcripts and documents according to the predefined parameter categories. Each piece of evidence is mapped into the domain characterisation table under the relevant parameter(s). Where new themes emerge that do not fit, the table is flexibly updated. The result is a structured mapping of expert knowledge: e.g. under “Ethics” themes like bias mitigation, transparency requirements, and clinician accountability is recorded. This organised mapping process ensures that raw insights are translated into a digestible format (the domain parameters) that can guide design. It effectively converts domain’s implicit and explicit knowledge into a shareable reference.

Documentation and validation: The outputs of the industry-level analysis are documented. The core artefact is the domain characterisation table and exploration tool, which enumerates each parameter (row) with its domain-specific details, examples, and references. To validate the captured information, we conduct a member-checking exercise: sharing the draft findings with a subset of the experts to confirm accuracy and completeness (does the summary of “Ethics” truly reflect AI concerns? did we miss any major regulatory guideline?). Feedback is incorporated, resulting in a vetted

industry-level knowledge base. This documentation is treated as a “living document”; as the industry evolves (new laws, emerging ethical guidelines, shifts in practice), the table can be updated. For reuse, the documentation is made accessible to future project teams.

4. Applied examples: AI-CDSS case-studies

To demonstrate the practical utility of the proposed framework, we present two real-world design studies in healthcare that both applied and contributed to the development of the domain characterisation knowledge base. In both cases, the framework supported early-stage scoping, stakeholder alignment, and informed iterative development. The framework was applied with the consideration of the evaluation criteria defined in Table 3.

4.1. Case 1: AI-CDSS for Neurological Condition, visualising patient data for better prediction and care

The EU TARA project [TAR] involved the development of an AI-enabled clinical decision support system to assist with migraine care by predicting attacks based on patient-generated data. The team drew upon the domain characterisation knowledge base to identify and structure relevant ethical, regulatory, data governance and other parameters. These informed interview protocols and workflows for design of explainable AI outputs. In particular, ethical AI expectations, data quality standards, and stakeholder-specific visualisation needs were modelled using a domain knowledge graph aligned with the framework.

Insights gathered during stakeholder interviews (clinicians, data stewards, patients, and researchers) were mapped to existing parameters and led to refinements in the ethical oversight and user role components of the knowledge base. Feedback from stakeholders confirmed that the structured representation helped clarify compliance responsibilities and informed ethical approval. The project’s ethics board and funder endorsed the framework as part of a risk mitigation process, underscoring its relevance and transferability.

4.2. Case 2: Data Capture and Analytics for an International Clinical Trial

In a multi-country clinical trial [STE], the research team faced diverse regulatory, infrastructural, and stakeholder-specific demands. By leveraging the industry-level domain characterisation outputs, including regional legal obligations, stakeholder roles, and future data reuse considerations, the team conducted individual and group interviews with trial managers, data security officers, and regional site leads. The domain characterisation map informed both the interview structure and the iterative design of a bespoke data collection and monitoring system.

The project made direct use of domain parameters related to patient consent and functional requirements. Iterative contributions from this case refined the knowledge base’s entries on consent, connectivity constraints, and evolving reuse policies. In turn, the refined parameters accelerated prototype validation and improved cross-team design harmonisation. Both cases illustrate how the two-phase framework enables feedback loops: knowledge is consumed to scaffold design, then updated through real-world reflection and new insights.

Figure 3: Evolution and reuse of domain characterisation parameters across literature, Industry Precondition study, and Two AI-CDSS Case Studies. The Figure shows how the foundational parameter categories were reused, refined, or introduced across methodological stages.

Table 3: Success criteria for assessing the framework’s impact, with alignment to the two applied cases.

Success Criterion	Case-Study 1: Neurology AI-CDSS	Case-Study 2: Clinical Trial Platform
Reduced ramp-up time	Precondition inputs accelerated discovery of ethical and compliance needs	Enabled rapid prototyping aligned with key decision maker expectations
Stakeholder alignment	Multi-role stakeholder needs structured, but needed further detailed interviews	Better understanding of cross-functional needs, but new parameters emerged
Problem scoping clarity	Explainability requirements emerged via ethical guidance analytics	Trial system architecture shaped by task-role-data constraints from the knowledge base, reduced number of use-cases
Regulatory compliance integration	Workflow aligned with GDPR, EU AI Act, and explainability mandates	Design aimed at meeting multi-jurisdictional consent and data privacy expectations
Reusability and knowledge contribution	Stakeholder data added to ethical constraints parameters	Contributed new entries on consent, Data Management role, organisation-specific data governance policies

The learning from the design study informed iterative modifications to the methodology and creation of a protocol for visualisation designers to conduct design studies in complex domains with two-phase approach.

5. Discussion and methodology recommendations

This work addresses a persistent methodological blind spot in visualisation research: the lack of formal mechanisms for capturing and reusing domain knowledge across design studies in complex, real-world settings. By decoupling domain characterisation from project-specific design, our two-phase framework introduces the characterisation layer - a reusable, transferable process artefact that augments existing methodologies such as the Nine-Stage Framework. The value lies not only in improving individual project out-

comes, but in supporting a cumulative research across design studies.

Critically, the framework formalises a practice that has long been recommended but rarely operationalised: early, structured understanding of contextual constraints. Our contribution is to scaffold this understanding into a repeatable and generalisable process, reducing the reliance on ad-hoc stakeholder engagement and opaque onboarding phases. The first-stage artefact – a domain characterisation layer – transforms expert wisdom and institutional knowledge into shareable infrastructure, supporting both rapid project scoping and methodological transparency.

This structure also aims to enhance comparability across studies. By introducing standardised representations of sociotechnical factors, the framework positions visualisation research for more

meaningful meta-analysis, reuse in education, and reproducibility in practice. Its compatibility with established frameworks ensures methodological continuity while addressing new demands for impact, ethics, and long-term alignment in design work.

Figure 3 synthesises how domain characterisation parameters evolved across methodological stages, illustrating where key elements were reused, refined, or contextually introduced. This visual trace supports our argument that sustainable visual analytics design in regulated domains requires iterative contextualisation, not one-time domain capture.

The two-phase framework supports better alignment by decoupling general, domain-level requirements from project-specific exploration, ensuring that foundational parameters - such as regulatory obligations, stakeholder roles, data governance, and ethical constraints - are addressed systematically before design begins. This mitigates misalignments that often arise when researchers rely solely on informal onboarding or incomplete early interviews. By externalising and standardising these upstream considerations, the framework allows visualisation teams to engage with domain experts using a shared vocabulary and a well-scoped problem space, reducing ambiguity and increasing relevance of design decisions from the outset.

It also enables a faster ramp-up for new projects by making reusable, validated domain knowledge immediately available. Instead of rediscovering context-specific constraints or stakeholder needs through each individual collaboration, researchers can draw on a curated domain characterisation layer that reflects prior analysis and expert synthesis. This allows teams to quickly identify viable design problems, anticipate organisational or ethical barriers, and allocate effort to problem-specific novelty rather than baseline understanding. For domains like healthcare, where access to experts is constrained and exploratory cycles are costly, this structured reuse substantially accelerates project momentum.

Finally, the approach promotes a better comparability across studies by standardising how domain context, stakeholder structure, and task environments are represented. By encouraging researchers to report and structure their design studies according to the same parameter schema, the framework facilitates meta-analyses, cross-study reflection, and knowledge accumulation within the field. This comparability also supports reproducibility and transparency - critical goals in visualisation research - by making the contextual assumptions and domain-specific constraints of each study explicit. Over time, this contributes to a shared repository of design practice that strengthens both methodological rigour and practical impact.

6. Limitations

While the framework provides a structured foundation for improving alignment between industry experts and researchers and across design studies and efficiency, it also presents several limitations. First, the abstraction of domain knowledge into reusable parameters inherently risks oversimplifying nuanced, site-specific practices. Domain contexts - especially in fields like AI-CDSS - can vary substantially between institutions or regions, meaning that the generalisations captured at the industry level risk to not fully account for all case contingencies. Second, the current version of the

framework is derived primarily from literature analysis and structured synthesis and AI-CDSS domain application; it has not yet undergone broad empirical validation across diverse project teams or institutional settings. To prove generalisability, the methodology should be instantiated and tested beyond AI-CDSS, ideally in another AI-regulated field (e.g., AI for legal compliance) and a non-AI yet complex domain (e.g., digital infrastructure in disaster response). This comparative approach would ensure the methodology is not overfitted to AI in healthcare alone.

It's also important to stress the evolving nature of the domain characterisation library components. Our research project started in 2021 and continued until 2025 and beyond, and as a consequence vocabulary evolved and, as an example, even the colloquial understanding of the term AI shifted from 'deep learning' towards 'generative models and agents'.

7. Conclusions and Further Work

This paper introduces a two-phase framework combining Sedlmair et al.'s Nine-Stage process with Munzner's Nested Model, that captures and reuses key domain parameters across literature, industry pre-conditions and two AI-CDSS case studies. As a methodological artefact, it fills a gap in visualisation research by structuring long-term, cross-project collaboration, with the aim to enhance rigour, accelerate onboarding, and lay the foundation for scalable meta-analysis and cumulative insights.

Future work should focus on operationalising and improving on the framework through interactive tools, empirical field testing, and longitudinal deployment across multiple design study contexts. One immediate step in our work is the development of a database-backed knowledge base with an interactive tools that allows visualisation researchers to query, filter, and adapt domain characterisation parameters to their specific needs. This would also support structured feedback loops, enabling continuous refinement of the framework as more use cases are logged. Further empirical studies - such as A/B comparisons between teams using the framework and those following unstructured practices - could provide evidence of its impact on design quality, stakeholder satisfaction, and project efficiency. In parallel, adapting the framework to other domains beyond healthcare would test its generalisability and help refine the granularity of its parameter structure.

Finally, the integration of this framework into the broader design study lifecycle opens opportunities for methodological advances in documentation and reproducibility. By embedding domain context explicitly into research outputs (e.g., via metadata appendices or shared domain profiles), future visualisation papers could align more directly with open science practices. This may also help foster the emergence of community-curated, domain-specific characterisation layers that evolve collectively over time, further reducing entry barriers and enhancing the maturity of design study methodology as a scientific practice.

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